

THE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF SOLUTIONS CONTAINING ZINC HYDROXIDE AND SODIUM HYDROXIDE.

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The measurement of electrical conductivity of solutions containing ZnO and Na_2O in varying proportions has been made. It is inferred that sodium zincate exists in concentrated solutions but that it is hydrolysed when the solutions are diluted; the zinc hydroxide set free as a consequence of hydrolysis exists in the colloidal state and when a critical dilution is reached it separates in the crystalline or amorphous form.

The behaviour of amphoteric oxides towards alkalis has been the theme of investigation of a large number of research workers but even to this day doubt exists concerning the formation of alkali salts of these oxides. In many cases attempts at the isolation of the alkali salts have given rise to conflicting data. Even the nature of solutions of these oxides in those of the hydroxides of the alkali metals is not clearly understood. The conclusions which may be drawn from the existing data are : (a) these solutions contain alkali salts of the amphoteric oxides, (b) they are colloidal solutions of the amphoteric oxides in alkalis, and (c) they contain the oxide in a colloidal form as well as an alkali salt. A systematic investigation of this problem has, therefore, been undertaken and a beginning is made with the study of the behaviour of zinc oxide towards sodium hydroxide.

The electrical conductivity measurements have been utilised for elucidating the condition of amphoteric oxides in solutions of sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide by a number of investigators but its use in the study of solutions of zinc oxide in those of sodium hydroxide has not received sufficient attention.

Hantzsch (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1902, **30**, 289) measured the electrical conductivity of solutions obtained by adding a solution of sodium hydroxide to that of zinc sulphate until the precipitated zinc hydroxide completely dissolved and concluded that in these solutions zinc hydroxide was present in the colloidal state. Subsequently he modified his views (*ibid.*, 1912, **75**, 371) and stated that the formation of sodium zinc oxides was not improbable and that these solutions might contain both the physical and chemical entities.

Carrara and Vespignani (*Gazzetta*, 1900, **30**, 63) and also Chatterjee and Dhar (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1920, **16**, Appendix, p. 123) concluded from conductivity measurements that zinc hydroxide dissolved in caustic alkali

exists mainly as an alkali zincate. Snell (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 583) on the other hand inferred from the want of discontinuity in the equivalent conductivity ratio curves that no complexes are formed in these solutions. He has not given data at 30° which were obtained "with less satisfactorily regulated experimental conditions" and was unable to prepare solutions containing a higher ratio of ZnO : Na₂O than 0.4.

In the present investigation the electrical conductivity of solutions containing different amounts of zinc hydroxide and sodium hydroxide expressed as the ratios of ZnO and Na₂O has been measured at 30° between 9N and 1N for solutions containing a large proportion of sodium hydroxide and between 9N and 3N for solutions containing a large proportion of zinc oxide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Zinc Hydroxide.—Crystalline zinc hydroxide was prepared according to the method of Dietrich and Johnstone (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 1419). These workers have not given sufficient details of the conditions of crystallisation and hence, after trial experiments, the following procedure was evolved which gave an yield of about 75%.

Zinc hydroxide was precipitated from recrystallised zinc sulphate (Merck's 'extra pure' quality) by ammonia, washed with hot water until free from sulphate ions and then dissolved in liquor ammonia (Merck's : *d* 0.888). The ammoniacal solution thus obtained was first kept under a bell-jar together with a beaker containing three parts of concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84) and two parts of water. The concentration of the acid was increased the next day to four parts of the acid and one of water. This acid was kept for about 36 hours and was then replaced by concentrated sulphuric acid. After about four days crystals began to separate and within a week a good crop of crystals was obtained. These crystals were removed, washed and preserved after drying. The mother liquor deposited zinc hydroxide in the amorphous form but it was redissolved in ammonia and crystallised as before. The crystals were analysed for loss of water as well as for zinc and the results (H₂O, 18.1%; ZnO, 81.90%) showed the product to be pure zinc hydroxide.

Estimation of Zinc.—Zinc was estimated volumetrically using potassium ferrocyanide, standardised against a solution of zinc (free from iron) as well as of zinc oxide in sulphuric acid. In these titrations diphenylbenzidine was used as an internal indicator. It was prepared according to the method of Marquerol and Murror (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, A i, 577) and dissolved in

concentrated sulphuric acid to give an 1% solution. The titrations were carried out as follows: A solution of sulphuric acid (3%) added to the solution containing zinc together with ammonium chloride (an excess of which was avoided as it retards the development of colour change) in order to obtain a sharp end-point and the whole was heated to 50-60° (cf. Kolthoff and Pearson, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1932, **4**, 147). Six drops of the indicator were then added and the solution of potassium ferrocyanide run in from a burette. At the end-point the colour is pale green.

Preparation of a Solution of Zinc Hydroxide in that of Sodium Hydroxide.—Preliminary experiments on the solubility of crystalline zinc hydroxide in solutions of sodium hydroxide showed that in low concentrations of the latter it was not appreciably soluble, but that a fairly large quantity of it dissolved in 10*N* sodium hydroxide. Calculated amount of crystalline zinc hydroxide required to form sodium zincate according to the equation

was added to a known volume of sodium hydroxide solution prepared by the method of Cornog (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 2573). This solution was prepared in a Jena glass flask the contents of which were shaken vigorously on a mechanical shaker for about 10-12 hours. The solution was then warmed on a water-bath for about two hours and after cooling, it was filtered through a sintered Jena glass funnel. The clear filtrate was transferred to a Jena glass flask which was corked with a rubber stopper and kept in a desiccator over soda lime.

Method for Analysing the Zincate Solution.—The stock solution of sodium zincate prepared as described above was analysed to determine the ratio ZnO: Na₂O. The solution (1 or 2 c. c.) was measured by means of a micro-pipette in a standard flask and treated with a known volume of standard sulphuric acid (0.2*N*—0.3*N*) sufficient to keep the precipitated zinc hydroxide in solution. Zinc was estimated according to the method already described; sodium sulphate present in the solution does not interfere in this estimation as shown by Kolthoff and Pearson (*loc. cit.*). From the amount of zinc estimated the corresponding amount of ZnO was obtained by calculation.

For the determination of the Na₂O content of the solution the sodium hydroxide contained in it was determined as follows: From the total

quantity of sulphuric acid originally taken, the uncombined acid and that which combined with zinc to form zinc sulphate were subtracted and hence the amount of sulphuric acid equivalent to the sodium hydroxide present in the zincate solution was obtained. In order to determine the free sulphuric acid referred to above, a known volume of the zincate solution in sulphuric acid was titrated against a solution of ammonia (about 0.15*N*), standardised just before taking the reading with the test solution, using methyl red as an indicator. It is important to note that blank experiments with solutions containing known amounts of free sulphuric acid and zinc sulphate, when titrated by the above method, gave entirely satisfactory results.

Solutions containing ZnO and Na₂O in the proportions (i) 1 : 1.76, (ii) 1 : 2.44, (iii) 1 : 3.03, (iv) 1 : 3.55 and (v) 1 : 4.05 were prepared from the stock solution in the following manner: A known volume of the stock solution was taken and to this the calculated volume of sodium hydroxide (16 *N*-18 *N*) was added so as to give (very nearly) a desired ratio of ZnO : Na₂O. It was made up to a known volume with freshly redistilled water free from carbon dioxide. It was then analysed according to the method described above and preserved in a Jena glass flask closed with a rubber stopper and placed in an atmosphere free from carbon dioxide.

The Measurement of Electrical Conductivity.—Since the zincate solutions were strongly alkaline, a conductivity cell of resistant glass made in the form of a U-tube of capacity 3 to 4 c. c. was used. The platinum electrodes were fixed in position and coated with platinum black. The cell constant was sufficiently high being of the order of 25.35 and it was checked every time before and after taking a set of conductivity readings.

The electrical conductivities of all the solutions containing the different ratios were measured at 30°. The temperature was kept constant within ±0.1° by means of a thermostat controlled by a toluene regulator. Several readings for the resistance of a solution were taken and the conductivity was calculated from the mean value.

In the case of the ratio 1 : 1.76 only four dilutions were possible. In 4*N* dilution crystals, which on analysis were found to be those of zinc hydroxide, separated out after three hours and in the case of 3*N* dilution, separation of the crystals was observed even earlier. In dilutions of 2*N* and more, amorphous precipitate of zinc hydroxide separated out.

In 3*N*, 2*N* and 1.5*N* dilutions of the ratio 1 : 2.44 crystalline zinc hydroxide separated out on standing for a sufficiently long time but in lower

dilutions amorphous zinc hydroxide separated before a reading could be taken.

As the sodium hydroxide content of the solutions increased in proportion to the zinc hydroxide present, separation of crystalline or amorphous zinc hydroxide took place at much higher dilutions. But in no case it was possible to take conductivity readings of solutions below 1N as in every case, when a dilution of 0.5 N was prepared, zinc hydroxide appeared almost immediately.

The equivalent conductivities in reciprocal ohms of the different solutions used in this investigation are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

	Ratios of ZnO : Na ₂ O in solutions				
	1:1.76.	1:2.44.	1:3.03.	1:3.55.	1:4.05.
9.41N*	13.14
9.20	...	18.49
9.50	20.37
9.48	23.10	...
9.47	24.54
8.0	21.23	26.18	29.30	32.75	35.36
6.0	38.45	47.19	48.60	53.37	55.98
4.0	63.50	73.70	78.70	83.80	86.40
3.0	79.92	91.50	101.2	104.8	108.2
2.0	...	117.9	121.2	134.8	136.5
1.5	...	129.95	138.2	149.3	152.3
1.0	149.8	173.1	176.9

DISCUSSION.

On a comparison of the data in Table I with those in Table II given below, in which the equivalent conductivity of sodium hydroxide at 30° obtained from the results of Bousfield and Lowry (*Phil. Trans.*, 1905, **A 204**, 205) is given, it will be found that the addition of zinc hydroxide diminishes the equivalent conductivity of sodium hydroxide.

TABLE II.

Equivalent conductivity of sodium hydroxide at 30°.

N	...	10	8	6	4	3	2	1.5	1
Eq. conductivity	...	30.0	49.4	75.8	111.0	132.5	160.0	176.8	196.0

* N = Normality of the solution in terms of its NaOH content.

This decrease in the conductivity of sodium hydroxide may be explained on the disappearance of a part of the mobile hydroxyl ions due to the formation of sodium zincate according to the following reaction given for the simplest salt:

On this assumption it may be expected that, for a given concentration, an increase in the relative amount of zinc hydroxide from the ratio, 1 : 4.05 to 1 : 1.76 would give rise to more of sodium zincate leading to a diminution in the conductivity and this is in accord with the experimental results. But according to Hantzsch (*loc. cit.*) zinc hydroxide dissolved in sodium hydroxide exists in the colloidal state. On this postulate the disappearance of a part of the mobile hydroxyl ions may be explained as being due to their adsorption on the colloidal entities. An examination of the Tyndall cone in solutions of different concentrations showed that practically no cone was visible in 8N solution but that its intensity increased as the solution was diluted. It appears probable that sodium zincate exists in concentrated solutions but undergoes hydrolysis when they are diluted. The zinc hydroxide, set free as a consequence of hydrolysis, exists in the colloidal state and when the critical dilution is reached it separates in the crystalline or amorphous form. The increase in the equivalent conductivity with dilution for all solutions containing the different ratios of ZnO: Na₂O is to be attributed to the regeneration of the mobile hydroxyl ions as a result of the hydrolysis of sodium zincate on dilution.

When the equivalent conductivity is plotted against the ratio ZnO:Na₂O curves are obtained which are nearly linear and concave towards the ratio axis as observed by Snell (*loc. cit.*). The absence of a change in direction of these curves probably indicates that sodium zincate is present in all the solutions investigated. It appears that a change in direction of the ratio-equivalent conductivity curves is to be expected when there is a transition from a solution containing no salt to one in which a salt is formed or from a solution containing one salt to another containing a different salt. It is incorrect to conclude, as done by Snell (*loc. cit.*), that no complexes exist in these solutions just because of the absence of discontinuity in the ratio-equivalent conductivity curves.